

TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The teaching of English as a foreign language to young learners is a complex and multifaceted task that requires careful consideration of the learner's age, cognitive development, and language learning style. In addition to these factors, the psychological factors that influence language learning also play an important role in the success of language teaching. In this article, we will explore the psychological factors that influence language learning in young learners, including motivation, anxiety, and learning style. We will also examine the impact of these factors on the effectiveness of language instruction, and discuss potential solutions for addressing these challenges. Finally, we will provide recommendations for best practices in the teaching of English to young learners, including the importance of creating a positive and supportive learning environment. This article will provide a comprehensive overview of the teaching of English to young learners as a foreign language, and will highlight the importance of considering both the learner's age and cognitive development, as well as their psychological factors, in order to promote successful language learning.

Key Words: young learners, adolescents, enthusiastic, meta-language, psychological factors, negligence, Total Physical Response.

Introduction: It is important for children to learn English from a young age as it is considered to be most important means of communication in the world. The awareness of English will help to open numerous doors in the future and will be advantageous when it comes to the future professional life.

Learner's age is an important factor in establishing suitable methods of teaching for each age group has its individual features and characteristics.

Young children do not know much and they are like blank sheet of paper. Compared to adolescents and adults, children's interests are narrower, restricted primarily to themselves, their immediate surroundings, their families, and their friends. The first key thing that all teachers should remember is that the teaching of children and the teaching of adults, both in technique and in attitude are entirely different propositions. Some differences are immediately obvious:

children are often more enthusiastic and lively as learners. They want to please the teacher rather than their peer group. They will have a go at an activity even when they don't quite understand why or how. However, they also lose interest more quickly and are less able to keep themselves motivated on tasks they find difficult. Children do not find it as easy to use language to talk about language, in other words, they do not have the same access as older learners to meta-language that teacher can use to explain about grammar or discourse.

There are some language teaching characteristics of young learners:

- even if they do not understand specific words, they understand the overall meaning of the information they get. They use this aptitude to study their mother tongue as well;

- they learn with all of their senses at the same time. Touching, smelling, and investigating anything is the finest method to learn and understand it. They learn from what they see and hear, as well as having the opportunity to touch and interact with it;

- they have a short attention span. Activities that continue more than 10 minutes bore kids, therefore the session must be exciting and full of varied jobs and activities;

- they are generally excited in learning and exploring their surroundings;

- they have a desire to be seen and regarded as individuals, as well as to be rewarded;

- they are resourceful in their use of limited language resources. Halliwell (1992:4) uses the example of a four-year-old boy stating "Switch off the light" to demonstrate children's ingenuity in employing means of communication they already know. It is the desire to communicate that drives children to generate new words for their own use;

- they learn indirectly most of the time, i.e. they are not concentrating on learning the phrase, but rather on guessing the correct one. They are not paying attention to the words, yet they retain the phrases;

- they enjoy having fun, and their mind is ready for any game or activity since they enjoy envisioning and fantasizing. They also enjoy imitating and making amusing noises with linguistic sounds;

- they enjoy conversing and exchanging views with people;

- they are excellent imitators; the teacher's purpose is to urge them to do it in English. Children employ echoing as a crucial tactic when learning a foreign language;

A teacher must know a few things in order to teach others. One of the most fundamental is technique, which refers to the approaches that he or she can employ to effectively teach a subject, in this case English;

Young learners learn best when they play games. They will be eager if they are taught through exciting activities or by being part in activities. They enjoy playing and learn best when they are having fun. Thus, Total Physical Response (TPR) by James Asher (1977) is an excellent method for teaching English, particularly to very young learners. This strategy keeps youngsters engaged in the learning process by connecting language to physical activity. Total Physical Response provides several advantages, especially for beginners and young learners. It is a way of teaching language that is based on the synchronization of voice and action; it seeks to teach language via physical (motor) activity. This method was developed by James Asher, a psychology professor at San Jose State University in California. It draws on several traditions, including developmental psychology, learning theory, and humanistic pedagogy, as well as Harold and Dorothy Palmer's language teaching procedures proposed in 1925. Consider these predecessors to Total Physical Response briefly.

TPR works well in the classroom:

- Vocabulary, especially verbs
- Difficult to describe activities (for example, wriggle, slide, and launch)
- Storytelling and narrative language
- Imperatives and classroom language

TPR is essentially learning via the teacher's spoken instructions to the students. The primary principle is that students are not forced to speak; their major role is to listen to and respond to the teachers' instructions in the foreign language, and only if they feel ready, may they begin speaking in that language. Here are some instances of such instructions: (Larsen Freeman):

“Bring me chalk from the box that lies on the desk”, “Go fast towards the door and hit it”, “Come to the blackboard and draw an apple” etc. The teacher speaks to the students using commands till everyone respond correctly and then one of the students can start giving instructions to his fellow students.

Moreover, using stories in foreign language teaching is of great value as they are naturally acquired and contextualized (Slatterly & Willis, 2001). Stories use a “holistic approach to language teaching and learning that places a high premium on children’s involvement with rich, authentic uses of the foreign language” (Cameron,2001:159). Cameron (2001) indicates a mental processing called ‘mentalese’ which is used in formulating meaning language independently.

Therefore, when children are told a story in foreign language, they are able to get the gist and summarize it with the help of visuals in their first language. However, it is not probable to narrate the story in the target language. Speaking is far demanding than listening and grasping the meaning is not enough to retell the story. While as Pinter (2008) states meaning focused input is crucial, it has also high importance to ensure production with language focus activities, though.

The most crucial factor for young learners is that TPR brings language to life and makes language learning pleasurable.

THE INFLUENCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS ON LANGUAGE TEACHING

Language is essential for transmitting thoughts, views, attitudes, emotions, and facts in any setting, particularly amongst people. A great deal of study has been conducted to evaluate the effects of psychological elements such as error fear, shyness, and low self-motivation on language acquisition, and the data shows that psychology plays an important role in language learning. As a result, an attempt is made to explore psychological elements and their impact on language learning.

During the process of learning a foreign language there are some psychological factors like motivation, interest, attitude, personality traits that influence the learning. That is because, from my point of view all language learners should be motivated intrinsically and extrinsically and also teacher should teach them according to their interests and also their age. We know that the way of language learning is different in language learners, that is why teacher should be flexible every time and try to find the most appropriate way of teaching for their learners. And teacher also should know the psychological features including motivation, interest, attitude, empathy, personality traits of their language learners.

The introduction of early foreign language training is based on children's inherent proclivity for languages and their emotional willingness to acquire them, according to psychologists and physiologists. A youngster learns a foreign language more readily than an adult, according to both locals [3] and foreign psychologists [2]. In this situation, they are frequently associated to preschool and primary school age children's sensitivity to learning common languages, particularly foreign languages. The duration of the sensitive period is calculated differently for different researchers: Penfield and Roberts describe it as 4 to 8 years, whereas Eliot defines it as 1.5 to 7 years. Children at this age are distinguished by a natural curiosity and a desire to learn new things. They are

more adaptable and faster than later stages of language acquisition. With age, a person's sensitivity to sense noises and capacity to reproduce them declines, as does short-term memory, as well as the ability to see and, most crucially, the ability to hear. A speech therapist is a youngster under the age of nine. What works best at a young age is that a kid may learn to pronounce foreign sounds, words, and intonation without stress if he or she continually listens to and imitates speech in a foreign language.

The success of teaching foreign languages to children depends on the following psychological factors:

a. Intelligence.

The term "intelligence" has traditionally been used to refer to performance on certain kinds of tests. These tests are often associated with success in school, and a link between intelligence and second language learning has sometimes been reported.

b. Aptitude.

Aptitude is characterized as the ability to learn quickly. We may hypothesize that a learner with high aptitude may learn with greater ease and speed.

c. Learning Style.

The term 'learning style' has been used to describe an individual's natural, habitual, and preferred way of absorbing, processing, and retaining new information and skills. Some people cannot learn and absorb knowledge without seeing it ('visual' learners). Other learners seem to learn best 'by ear' ('aural' learners). For others, a physical action such as miming or role-play seems to help the learning process ('kinesthetic' learners). These are perceptually-based learning styles.

d. Personality.

A number of personality characteristics have been proposed as likely to affect second language learning. It is often argued that an extroverted person is well suited to language learning. Another aspect of personality that has been studied is inhibition. It has been suggested that inhibition discourages risk-taking, which is necessary for progress in language learning. Furthermore, learner anxiety-feelings of worry, nervousness, and stress that many students experience when learning a second language has been extensively investigated. Recent research investigating learner anxiety in second language classrooms acknowledges that anxiety is more likely to be dynamic and dependent on particular situations and circumstances. Several other personality characteristics

such as self-esteem, empathy, dominance, talkativeness, and responsiveness have also been studied.

e. Motivation (Intrinsic).

Motivation has been defined in terms of two factors: learners' communicative needs and their attitudes towards the second language. If learners need to speak the second language in a wide range of social situations or for career development, they will perceive the communicative value of the second language and will therefore be motivated to acquire proficiency in it. Likewise, if learners have good attitudes towards the speakers of the language, they will desire more to learn it.

f. Motivation (Extrinsic).

Teachers also influence on students' behavior and motivation in language learning. A teacher is one of students' reasons for studying the second language or having good attitudes toward the language learning. Teachers may give a positive contribution to students' motivation to learn if classrooms are places that students enjoy coming to because the content is interesting and relevant to their age and level of ability, the learning goals are challenging yet manageable and clear, and the atmosphere is supportive.

g. Culture and Status.

There is some evidence that students in situations where their own culture has a lower status than that of the culture in which they are learning the language make slower progress. Social factors at a more general level affect motivation, attitudes, and language learning success. One such factor is the social dynamic or power relationship between the languages.

Learning a foreign language is one of the most challenging goals for the human brain. It is necessary not only to mentally transfer linguistically constructs and structures from the native language to a foreign one, but also to learn to think in a foreign language. Problems in learning a new language can come from internal and external factors which can influence students' motivation to learn.

The primary issue is negligence. If parents do not pay attention to their children, overlook their ambitions, or do not provide the care that their children want and want, this might lead to psychological and social difficulties in the future. Because they lack conversational abilities with others, their listening and speaking skills will be particularly detrimental. They may also struggle with cognitive development.

Psychological issues are another prevalent aspect. It is undeniable that any psychological or behavioral issues prevent a child's capacity to grasp language.

Any kid with a behavioral condition, such as antisocial personality disorder or autism, which causes a lack of reaction to others due to a restricted capacity or disinclination to communicate and socially, may have certain limitations. This occurs anytime they attempt to communicate with people and comprehend social expressions. If your child has a psychiatric problem, you should provide opportunities for socialization. Otherwise, the disease can affect your child's capacity to acquire and interpret language.

Another important element that is a twin of psychiatric disease is social anxiety. His comprehension capacity will decline if he does not engage or speak with other children and adults. Any youngster who is anxious or shy may have difficulties with their language development. Because they lack the practices. They can overcome their social anxiety and engage in language acquisition by giving everyday social chances.

Psychology is an essential tool for deep understanding of human's psyche. Using this tool by teachers in process of educating and by students for getting knowledge makes learning easier and more effective.

CONCLUSION

The teaching of English for young learners actually has many aspects to concern more than these mentioned above. It is true that the teacher can influence the students in learning English. It is also connected to the methods in teaching English language for young learners. This article has examined the issues with teaching young learners, and how they differ from older learners and suggesting effective method of teaching them. The main ways the classroom needs to be adapted for young learners are through different activities, as well as, psychological factors.

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